

Potassium fertilizer experiments in farmer fields

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We studied rice response to potash application on farmer fields in Dera Ismail Khan district of the North West Frontier Province of Pakistan. Available potash at different sites was 100 to 250 ppm, and chloride content was 28 to 39 ppm. In the first experiment (Table 1) all levels of applied potash increased rice yields significantly. Some benefits may have been derived from K application.

In the second experiment, application of 135-40-37 kg NPK/ha produced the highest yield of 7.58 t/ha (Table 2).

Of two K sources (Table 2), K₂SO₄ was significantly better than KCl. □

Table 1. Effect of K application on paddy yield, Tarnab, Pakistan.^a

Treatment (kg/ha)			Yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase over N + P (t/ha)
N	P	K		
0	0	0	3.57 b	—
120	40	0	5.05 a	—
120	40	25	5.19 a	0.14
120	40	50	5.65 a	0.60
120	40	15	5.97 a	0.92
120	40	100	5.72 a	0.67
120	40	125	5.58 a	0.53

^a As of 5 experiments in 1979-81. ^b Separation of means by Duncan's Multiple Range Test at 5% level.

Table 2. Effect of fertilizer applications on paddy yield. Tarnab, Pakistan.

Treatment (kg/ha)			Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over N + P (t/ha)	Value of increased yield ^b (US\$)	Value-cost ^c ratio
N	P	K				
<i>NPK application^d</i>						
0	0	0	4.95 c	—	—	—
135	0	0	6.07 b	—	—	—
135	40	0	6.97 ab	—	—	—
135	40	37	7.58 a	0.61	74.20	12.97
<i>K₂SO₄ and KCl application^e</i>						
120	35	0	4.91 c	—	—	—
120	35	83 (KCl)	5.52 b	0.61	74.72	9.34
120	35	83 (K ₂ SO ₄)	6.11 a	1.21	148.22	12.35

^a Separation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level. ^b Value of paddy = US\$122.5/t. ^c Fertilizer cost = K₂SO₄: US\$12/83 kg K, US\$ = 8/83 kg K. Value-cost ratio is for KCl:potash only. ^d Av of 3 experiments in 1979-81. ^e Av of 25 experiments in 1979-81.

Dual cropping azolla in lowland rice

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We evaluated azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer for lowland rice IR20 in the field at TNRRI in winter 1982-83. The soil had pH 6.8 with CEC 24.5 meq/100 g and 5.9 ppm available P (Olsen), dry soil basis. Eighty kg P and 31 kg potash/ha were applied basally.

Azolla was inoculated with 30 and 60 kg N/ha and results were compared with four N treatments (see table). Urea N was applied 50% basally and in 2 equal splits 20 and 40 d after transplanting, and 500 kg fresh *Azolla pinnata*/ha was applied 1 wk after

Effect of azolla on grain yield of IR20, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
No N control	2.8
30	3.2
60	3.7
90 N	3.9
30 N + azolla	3.7
60 N + azolla	3.9
LSD (0.05)	
	0.7

transplanting. Azolla was allowed to multiply and decompose in the field. A maximum biomass of 790 g/m² was recorded at a multiplication rate of 195 g/m² per week. N content of fresh azolla was 0.37%.

Dual cropping 500 kg fresh azolla/ha with 60 kg N gave a yield equal to that with 90 kg N (see table). □

Environment and its influence

Screening for shade tolerance in rice seedlings

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Rice plants are subjected to various degrees of low light intensity when grown under coconut trees, in pockets of forest land, when mixed with other crops, and when grown during the wet

season. Rice production in these situations is poor because solar radiation for crop growth is insufficient. Some degree of shade tolerance may overcome this situation. We sought to determine suitable morphological and physiological parameters to use in screening for shade tolerance and to develop a suitable screening method for use in the greenhouse.

Ten pregerminated seeds of 10 varieties were sown in a row in each 40 × 25 × 15-cm plastic tray filled with 6 cm of

fine Maahas clay. The experiment was in three replications. For 14 d, the 10-d-old seedlings were subjected to 3 degrees of shading: 55, 72, and 86%. Two sets were given continuous dark treatment for 7 or 14 d.

Plants grown in 55% shade produced 50% less dry weight than those in full sun. Fifty-five percent shading was judged to be critical. IR52 and FR13A showed the least reduction in dry matter at that level (see table). At the end of